

EFFECTIVENESS AND IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES OF E-HEALTH INTERVENTIONS IN CANCER PAIN MANAGEMENT: A SCOPING REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Pain remains one of the most prevalent and debilitating symptoms experienced by individuals with cancer, adversely affecting their quality of life, treatment adherence, and psychosocial well-being. In Indonesia and other low-resource settings, cancer pain management continues to face systemic challenges, including limited access to palliative care, inadequate opioid availability, low health and digital literacy, and regulatory constraints. With the growing integration of digital technology in healthcare, electronic health (e-Health) interventions such as mobile applications, telemedicine, and mHealth platforms have emerged as promising strategies. This study aims to systematically map the types of e-Health interventions applied in cancer pain management, examine their effectiveness, and identify implementation barriers and opportunities, particularly in developing country contexts. **Method:** This study used a scoping review approach following the PRISMA-ScR guideline and PCC framework (Population: cancer patients; Concept: e-Health interventions; Context: pain management). Literature was searched in four databases (PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar) for studies published between 2016 and 2024. Ten studies met the inclusion criteria and were analyzed. **Results:** Identified e-Health interventions included mobile applications, telemedicine, CBT-based tools, telerehabilitation, and integrated digital ecosystems. Most interventions were effective in reducing pain intensity, enhancing self-management, improving adherence, and providing psychosocial support. Interactive features such as chat functions and video-based coping strategies were especially impactful. **Conclusion:** e-Health presents a promising solution for cancer pain management by supporting both physical and psychosocial aspects of care. With proper adaptation and integration, these interventions can strengthen oncology services and patient outcomes in low-resource environments.

Keywords: E-Health, Cancer Pain, Telemedicine, e-Health interventions, Scoping Review.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death in the world, including in Indonesia. According to the Global Cancer Observatory (Globocan), in 2022 there were more than 396,914 new cases of cancer and 234,511 deaths due to cancer in Indonesia, with a trend that continues to increase every year [1]. One of the main problems that cancer patients face is pain. Approximately 55% of patients in all stages of the disease and more than 80% in patients with advanced cancer [2]. In Indonesia, many cancer patients come for treatment in advanced conditions, so the prevalence of severe pain is very high [3].

Uncontrolled pain causes physical, psychological, social, and economic distress, both for the patient and his family [4]. Studies in Indonesia show that cancer pain is associated with decreased quality of life, sleep disorders, anxiety, and even decreased adherence to treatment.[5] In addition,

cancer patients in Indonesia often have to travel long distances to get pain treatment, adding to the cost and time burden [3].

Despite cancer pain management guidelines, the implementation of cancer management still faces many obstacles, such as a lack of palliative facilities, limited access to opioids, lack of trained health workers, and low public health literacy (Oldenmenger et al., 2019). The stigma of

opioid use and strict regulation are also a big challenge in Indonesia, so many patients do not get adequate pain management [7]. This situation was exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic, when many cancer patients were forced to postpone visits or could not access optimal health services [8].

A number of international studies have confirmed that e-Health interventions, such as mobile applications, telemedicine, and remote monitoring, have been proven to improve pain monitoring, patient education, and communication between patients and healthcare workers. For example, Wang et al. (2018) through systematic review showed the effectiveness of digital interventions in helping symptom and pain management in cancer patients [9] While Oldenmenger et al. (2018) found that e-Health facilitates early detection of pain and accelerates intervention in patients with advanced cancer [6]. Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Lozano et al. (2020) showed that the use of mobile apps significantly reduced pain intensity and strengthened patient involvement in symptom management [11].

The use of telemedicine has begun to grow rapidly since the COVID-19 pandemic, especially for general consultations and online oncology services [8]. However, most research is still focused on clinical aspects in general or on other chronic diseases, and has not specifically explored the implementation of e-Health in the context of cancer pain management as a whole. In Indonesia itself, systematic studies that map the types of e-Health interventions and their effectiveness on cancer pain are still very limited. In addition, challenges and obstacles to implementation in developing countries, such as limited digital infrastructure and low digital literacy, have not been discussed in depth in the local and global literature.

Other research also supports the effectiveness of e-Health in reducing pain and sleep disturbances in cancer survivors Chen et al. (2022) affirm that telemedicine is effective in reducing pain intensity and improving the quality of life of cancer patients [12]. Meanwhile, Evenepoel et al. (2023) showed that e-Health interventions are able to effectively manage pain in both cancer patients and patients with musculoskeletal disorders [13]. Van der Houwen et al. (2024) in a scoping review show that telehealth has been widely adopted in cancer care, although implementation challenges are still considerable in developing countries due to limited infrastructure and resources [14]. Ostertag et al. (2024) also look at the benefits of integrated psychosocial and physical interventions through e-Health in chronic pain management, providing important insights to apply in the context of cancer [15].

This study aims to systematically review forms of e-Health interventions in pain management in cancer patients, evaluate their effectiveness and benefits, and identify challenges and opportunities for their implementation in a global context and especially in developing countries such as Indonesia.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study follows the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) and uses a framework developed by Arksey and O'Malley, with a PCC (Population, Concept, Context) approach [16]. The components of PCC in this study consist of: Population, which is cancer patients, Concept, which is e-Health intervention, and Context, which is pain management. The inclusion criteria used in the study selection were: (1) studies that discussed e-Health interventions specifically aimed at pain management in cancer patients; (2) studies with quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-methods designs; (3) articles in English or Indonesian; and (4) published in the period from 2016 to 2024.

Exclusion criteria include: (1) studies that do not specifically address cancer pain management with e-Health; (2) publications in the form of editorials, narrative reviews, readers' letters, and conference abstracts without full-text

Table 2 Keywords and Boolean

DATABASE	BOOLEAN SEARCH STRING
PubMed	("cancer" OR "oncology" OR "cancer patients") AND ("eHealth" OR "digital health" OR "mobile application" OR "telemedicine" OR "mHealth") AND ("pain management" OR "pain control" OR "pain relief" OR "pain intervention")
Scopus	("cancer" OR "oncology" OR "cancer patients") AND ("eHealth" OR "digital health" OR "mobile application" OR "telemedicine" OR "mHealth") AND ("pain management" OR "pain control" OR "pain relief" OR "pain intervention")
ScienceDirect	("cancer" OR "oncology" OR "cancer patients") AND ("eHealth" OR "mobile application" OR "mHealth" OR "telemedicine") AND ("pain management" OR "pain control" OR "pain intervention")

The selection process is carried out independently by two researchers, and any differences of opinion are resolved through discussion. A literature search was conducted in January 2025 using four main databases: PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. After the search process, the initial search results were obtained, 912 articles were obtained. Once the duplication is removed, there are 861 articles left that are selected by title and abstract. A total of 769 articles were removed for irrelevance, leaving 92 articles for full-text review. Furthermore, an assessment was carried out on the feasibility of full-text, and 77 articles were expelled because they did not meet the inclusion criteria. The final results showed that 15 articles were worth analyzing, but after further consideration, only 10 were actually eligible for inclusion in this scoping review.

Figure 1. Prisma Flowchart

3. RESULTS

A total of 10 articles have been extracted and analyzed based on the author's name, year of publication, type of e-Health intervention, main outcomes, reported benefits, and challenges or opportunities for implementation. The articles are presented narratively in Table 2.

No	Author (Year)	Research Objectives	Types of e-Health Interventions	Research Results	Effectiveness /Benefits	Challenges/ Opportunities
1	E. Ream <i>et al</i> (2020)	Evaluating the effect of nurse-led telephone interventions on the quality of life & symptoms (including pain) of cancer patients	Telephone (nurse-led)	Telephone interventions are effective in lowering anxiety, depression, and fatigue; However, the effects on pain are still varied across studies	Reduces depression, anxiety, fatigue; Results vary for pain	Evidence of effectiveness for limited pain, design heterogeneity
2	C. Zheng <i>et al</i> (2020)	Examining the effectiveness of mobile applications (chat features) for pain management of cancer patients	Mobile App	Apps with instant messaging significantly lower pain scores compared to controls; Improved compliance and pain reporting	Significantly lowers pain scores, especially with the chat feature	Some apps are less effective without chat features, limited validation
3	Kelleher <i>et al</i> (2019)	Testing the effectiveness of mHealth (video/app coping skills) in cancer pain control	mHealth (video, app)	mHealth program based on coping skills improves self-efficacy, reduces pain and anxiety in underserved cancer patients	Improved pain control, self-efficacy, feasible and patient acceptance	Lack of access to technology, the need for social media
4	Cascella <i>et al</i> (2022)	Analyze the satisfaction and benefits of using telemedicine in cancer patients (including pain)	Telemedicine (video)	Telemedicine improves patient satisfaction (80%+), speeds up access to pain services, and is	High patient satisfaction, increased access, service efficiency	Low digital literacy, dropout, need for a hybrid approach

		managem ent)		efficient for periodic monitoring		
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Table 2. Summary of Included Studies

5	J. Sketch <i>and all</i> (2019)	Assessing the usability & benefits of the INES application-DIO for monitoring breakthrough cancer pain (BTcP)	Mobile App (INES-DIO)	The use of the app improves BTcP pain reporting, more than 70% of patients find it easier to communicate symptoms to the doctor	Improved BTcP monitoring, easy to use, patient & physician acceptability	Need for the development of digital guidelines, educational content
6	Kelly <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Examine the effect of video/app-based coping skills on the pain, coping, and disability of underserved cancer patients	mHealth (video/app, coping skills)	The intervention significantly lowered pain scores, disability, and improved coping skills after 8 weeks, compared to controls	Reduce pain & disability, improve coping skills in the underserved	Broad implementation requires adjustment of local context, digital divide
7	Masiero <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Evaluating PainRELife, a new digital ecosystem for cancer pain management	Digital ecosystem (PainRELife)	Pilot study: Significant decrease in pain intensity; patient participation and adherence >85%; quality of life improved at 3 months	Decrease in pain intensity, improve participation & quality of life	Pilot study, need scalability, patient engagement

8	Hyland <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Testing the effectiveness of CBT-based mHealth on the pain & quality of life of adolescent cancer survivors	mHealth (CBT-app/videocall)	mHealth-CBT lowers pain, fatigue, distress and improves self-efficacy and physical function in the 12-week program	Lowers pain, fatigue, distress; Improve quality of life & self-efficacy	Adolescent adaptation, routine integration, long-term reporting
9	Lozano - Lozano <i>et al</i> (2020)	Assessing the effectiveness of telerehabilitation exercise (e-CUIDATE) on pain	Telehealth/Telerehab (e-CUIDATE)	Internet-based telerehabilitation exercise significantly reduced pain severity and interference, with effects	Telerehabilitation reduces pain severity & interference, improves quality of life	High adherence rate (>90%), challenges: internet access, adaptation of local culture

		reduction & quality of life		lasting up to 6 months		
10	Madi, <i>et al</i> (2023)	Explore mHealth's perceptions & experiences for social support & pain management of children with cancer	mHealth App (peer-based, anak)	Applications are accepted by both the child and the caregiver; reported to increase connectedness, pain reporting, but literacy barriers still exist	mHealth is well received, potential to improve connectedness and pain reporting	Barriers: digital literacy, privacy, language, apps must be child-friendly

Based on a review of 10 articles that met the inclusion criteria, it was found that the role of e-Health interventions in pain management in cancer patients can be grouped into five main themes, namely: (1) the form of e-Health intervention used, (2) effectiveness in reducing pain and improving self-management, (3) support for the psychosocial aspects of patients, (4) implementation challenges in various contexts, and (5) opportunities for future development of digital services.

3.1 Forms of e-Health Intervention in Cancer Pain Management

This scoping review identified different forms of e-Health interventions used in pain management in cancer patients. The most common form is a mobile application that comes with educational, pain reporting, and two-way communication features such as instant messaging [17][18]. In addition, coping skills-based interventions and cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) through apps or videos were also found in studies targeting adult patients and adolescent cancer survivors [19][20]. Other forms that were also identified include video-based telemedicine, nurse-led telephone support and online exercise-based telerehabilitation as well as integrated digital ecosystems such as PainRELife [21] [11] [22]. One study also involved the use of a peer support-based app for children undergoing cancer therapy [23].

3.2 The Effectiveness of Interventions in Reducing Pain and Improving Self-Management

Most of the e-Health interventions identified showed effectiveness in lowering pain and strengthening patients' abilities in self-management. Apps with interactive communication features such as chat have been shown to be effective in lowering pain scores and improving reporting compliance [17]. Other studies have shown that coping skills-based approaches and CBT can improve self-efficacy, reduce distress, and reduce pain-related disabilities, especially in underserved groups and cancer-related adolescents [24][19]. Exercise-based telerehabilitation interventions in Lozano-Lozano et al. (2020) also showed a decrease in pain severity and interference that lasted up to six months [11]. A pilot study by Masiero et al. (2024) shows that PainRELife can improve patient participation and adherence to treatment, as well as decrease pain intensity [22].

3.3 Psychosocial Support and Patient Quality of Life

In addition to reducing pain, some interventions also provide significant psychosocial support, especially in reducing anxiety, fatigue, and improving patients' quality of life. Telephone interventions by nurses in the Ream et al. (2020) study consistently lowered psychological symptoms such as

depression and anxiety, although effects on pain still varied [21]. Similarly, CBT-based interventions (Hyland et al., 2022) have been shown to reduce distress and fatigue and improve the physical function and quality of life of adolescent cancer survivors [19]. In the

child population, the mHealth application with a peer-based approach has also been reported to increase the sense of connectedness between patients, caregivers, and health workers [23].

3.4 Implementation Challenges: Access, Literacy, and Context Adaptation

Several challenges arise in the implementation of e-Health interventions, especially related to technology access, digital literacy, and suitability of user contexts. The study of Cascella et al. (2022) highlights low digital literacy and dropout risk as barriers to the widespread use of telemedicine [20]. Meanwhile, the Lozano-Lozano et al. (2020) study noted that limited internet access is the main obstacle in the success of telerehabilitation [11]. The study of Madi et al. (2023) also shows that apps for children require special attention to privacy, language, and child-friendly design [23]. In addition, some effective applications such as INES-DIO still requires content validation and implementation guidelines for healthcare workers [18].

3.5 Digital Services Development and Adoption Opportunities

Despite the challenges, the review also uncovered opportunities for the development of digital services in cancer pain management. The use of applications with educational features, real-time reporting, and psychosocial support shows the potential to be integrated into routine health care systems. The study of Masiero et al. (2024) underscores the importance of developing services that actively involve patients in pain management through a comprehensive digital approach [22]. Some studies also encourage hybrid models (a combination of digital and face-to-face services) to reach groups that are not yet fully prepared for digital transformation. In addition, community engagement, healthcare worker training, and user-based design are key to increasing the success of e-Health adoption in the future.

4. DISCUSSION

This scoping review shows that e-Health interventions in pain management in cancer patients have evolved significantly in the past decade, both in terms of technological form, population coverage, and clinical outcomes. The diversity of intervention forms found, from mobile applications to integrated digital ecosystems, reflects the flexibility and broad potential of these technologies to support comprehensive nursing services and symptom management.

The most prominent form of e-Health intervention is a mobile application designed to facilitate patient education, real-time pain reporting, and two-way communication between patients and healthcare workers. These findings support the reports of Oldenmenger et al. (2018) and Wang et al. (2018) which stated that the use of digital applications can improve early detection of symptoms and facilitate faster interventions [10] [12]. In addition, coping skills-based interventions and cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) adapted in digital form also expand the role of e-Health in the psychosocial and emotional aspects of cancer patients, not just physical. This approach shows that e-Health is not only a reporting medium, but also a therapeutic intervention tool that can be accessed independently.

The effectiveness of e-Health interventions in reducing pain and improving self-management is reflected in a number of studies that reported a decrease in pain scores, increased adherence, and strengthening of patients' coping capacity. Studies such as Zheng et al. (2020) and Masiero et al. (2024) show that two-way communication features and active patient engagement are key to the success of digital interventions [17] [22]. Even in underserved and adolescent populations, CBT-based applications and coping skills such as in the Kelleher et al. (2019) and Hyland et al. (2022) studies show significant positive impacts on self-efficacy, physical function, and quality of life.

On the other hand, the aspect of psychosocial support is also strengthened by e-Health interventions. Several studies, such as those conducted by Ream et al. (2020) and Madi et al. (2023),

show that digital apps can help reduce anxiety, fatigue, and improve connectedness between patients, families, and healthcare workers. This is in line with the principles of holistic nursing that place the emotional well-being of patients as an integral part of pain management. However, the implementation of e-Health interventions is inseparable from challenges. Obstacles such as limited internet access, low digital literacy, and lack of application content validation are recurring issues. The Lozano-Lozano et al. (2020) and Cascella et al. (2022) studies show that

technology gaps can hinder the success of interventions, especially in developing countries or communities with limited resources. In addition, the success of implementation also depends heavily on organizational readiness and system support, including training for health workers.

Nonetheless, the opportunity to develop and adopt digital services remains wide open. Several studies emphasize the importance of a hybrid approach, patient involvement in intervention design, and application integration into existing healthcare systems. This approach can overcome technological limitations while maintaining a humanistic aspect in service. In addition, the development of evidence-based technology use guidelines and supporting policies are also urgently needed to encourage widespread and sustainable adoption of e-Health.

Overall, e-Health offers innovative solutions in cancer pain management that are more flexible, scalable, and patient-centered. Nurses as frontline health workers have a strategic role in initiating, implementing, and evaluating these technology-based interventions to align with patient needs and service contextuality.

5. CONCLUSION

e-Health interventions have been shown to be effective in supporting pain management in cancer patients, either through reducing pain intensity, improving self-management, and psychosocial support. Although there are still implementation challenges, e-Health has great potential to be integrated into oncology services in a sustainable manner.

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